

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL METHOD FOR LARGE TRANSFORMATIONS OF REINFORCED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: Two approaches are presented to modelise and take into account in a finite element model the nonlinear mechanical behavior of the reinforcements and the matrix of composite materials and structures. Based on homogenization technique and a macro - micro approach, the first method requires the knowledge of experimental tensile stress-strain curves of the constituents and their Poisson's ratio. The second, of a very convenient use as it will be shown, is based on a combined exploitation of experimental data and finite element results. Few a steps of successive comparisons of these results are necessary to make it efficient and accurate enough. While the first approach is described in details only, the second was actually performed to simulate the response of a pressurized Aramid fiber-rubber composite cylinder. The details of this method and of the numerical tools are given and the results are discussed.

KEYWORDS: reinforced composite structures, material nonlinearities, large transformations, finite element modeling, experimental tests.

INTRODUCTION

One of the main difficulties one can face when attempting to modelise composite reinforced materials and structures under large loadings (especially when the constitutive material is highly flexible), is to introduce the nonlinear mechanical behavior of reinforcements and matrix in the numerical model. Although successful attempts were realized on a single reinforced (cord-rubber) ply, the problem becomes much more difficult when real physical structures are involved because of the too large size of the finite element model. Fig. 1 shows the structure under consideration in this paper.

Fig. 1: Description of the structure . Definition of the Axes and boundary conditions

This structure is an axisymmetric multilayer composite cylinder. Because of the symmetry with respect to plane $z = 0$ only its half part is modeled. Each constitutive layer is a reinforced Aramid fiber-rubber composite ply. The fiber's volume ratio, $V_f = 36\%$ and their orientation with respect to z - axis equals to $\pm 14^\circ$ alternatively in two successive plies. In a previous study [1] the author showed that if the mechanical behavior of the constituents and, consequently, of the composite plies is determined under the hypothesis of infinitesimal strains and displacements the numerical solution moves away from the experimental results (see Fig. 6), i.e., the elastic and linear approach becomes unsuitable. This phenomenon occurs at a relatively modest level of the internal pressure since that the fibers and the resin are submitted, locally, to high strain level.

In this paper we developed a finite element model in which the large strains and nonlinear behavior of aramid fiber (see Fig. 2_a) and rubber matrix (see Fig. 2_b) are taken into account. For that, we suggest two approaches : an Incremental Homogenization Method and a Multilinear Domain Approach. The last method was actually performed and led to sufficiently accurate results with fairly good agreement with the experimental ones.

Fig. 2_a. Aramid fiber behavior under uniaxial tensile test

Fig. 2_b. Rubber behavior under uniaxial tensile test

INCREMENTAL HOMOGENIZATION METHOD

The first approach called Incremental Homogenization Method (IHM) requires the knowledge of experimental tensile curves of fibers and matrix, their Poisson ratios, volume fraction of fibers (or matrix) and their local orientation inside the reinforced ply. The (IHM), based on a macro-micro process, is applied in several identical stages and could be summarized as following:

(i) Young's moduli and Poisson's ratio (E^f_1 , ν^f_1) for fibers and (E^r_1 , ν^r_1) for matrix are identified by classical experimental methods. Then, one homogenization technique, called Homogenization Technique of Periodic Cells Structures is performed [2], [3], to obtain the homogenized elastic moduli of the equivalent anisotropic (locally orthotropic in this case) material and denoted by the stiffness tensor $[Q^1]$. This technique was validated [1] in this case through significant experiments.

(ii) *Macroscopic* numerical simulation based on a finite element analysis is realized by introducing the $[Q^1]$ tensor and an incremental algorithm (Newton- Raphson) is used to solve the problem.

(iii) After each *small* increment, the *mesoscopic* (ply-scale) displacement, strain and stress fields solution of the numerical problem are known. We perform then the so called Localization Process [5] to be back to the *microscopic* scale: fiber and matrix. This process allows the determination of displacements, strains and stresses fields in fibers and matrix by using the macroscopic results obtained in the previous step (ii). The Localization Process can be applied, automatically, to each previously chosen relevant elementary volume (the finite element still the smallest) of the model. Using these results, we can extract the slope between the minimum and maximum strain values computed on the elementary volume directly identified on the experimental curves previously introduced in the computer memory.

Thus, we are able to identify the *new* Young's moduli (we are conscious of misusing the expression) of the fiber and the resin denoted by $(E^f_2)_k$ and $(E^r_2)_k$ for the k-th elementary volume : $\delta\Omega_k$. In this case, the variations of Poisson's ratios can reasonably be neglected. (If needed, the computed strain field can yield to the new values of those coefficients). Moreover the knowledge of the displacement field allows the determination of new volume ratio and the local orientation of the fibers.

(iv) The next step consists in applying the following test to each $\delta\Omega_k$:

$$\boxed{|(E^f_2)_k - (E^f_1)_k| \leq \epsilon_1 \text{ ? and } |(E^r_2)_k - (E^r_1)_k| \leq \epsilon_2 \text{ ?}}$$

If the test is satisfied, the load is incremented and the previous steps are reproduced. Otherwise, the ply mechanical behavior is determined like described in the step (i) by injecting the new computed input data. This incremental method could be performed as many times as necessary to reach the desired loading value.

Considerations about the Incremental Homogenization Method

The choice of the three fundamental parameters: Elementary volumes $\delta\Omega_k$ and the test parameters ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 falls to the operator. Nevertheless, this choice must consider, at least, two principal aspects : the estimated experimental uncertainties and the desired accuracy.

This method can be applied systematically and with a very high accuracy to such nonlinear problems and particularly when experimental results are not available on the entire composite structure under consideration. However, it induces high numerical cost when applied to realistic structures. Hence, a careful compromise should be found out between the desired accuracy of the results and the cost by acting, directly, on the fundamental parameters defined above.

In case experimental results are available for the whole structure one can perform a much easier and nevertheless efficient method, that is the multilinear domain approach. Before getting into details of this method we describe briefly the experimental tests carried out on the considered structure and used to perform this approach.

Description of the Experiments

The structure is submitted to an internal pressure denoted by P_i on its internal face (Γ_i) when the top and bottom faces (Γ_U), defined by $z = \pm H$, are built in (see Fig. 1). The load was incremented by constant fraction, $\delta P = 0.01$ MPa (0.1 bar). The total pressure loading was set to 0.39 MPa. At each load we measured the radial displacement (u_r) of the point denoted by M on fig. 1 and the z-component of the total reaction force (R_z) on the built in faces Γ_0 .

Multilinear Domain Approach

The basic idea of the Multilinear Domain Approach (MDA) when applied to composite materials and structures is to share the total strain intervals of the constituents in a finite number of domains in which the behavior can be approximated by an elastic and linear one. Thus, the nonlinear behavior of rubber and aramid fiber is assumed to be taken into account only through the variation of the tensile resistance of the constituents.

In the case under consideration, (see Fig. 2_a and Fig. 2_b) we exhibited 4 domains for the rubber matrix and 3 for the reinforcements (denoted by Romaine numbers).

In table 1 are summarized the different strain intervals and the measured values of the slopes. The Poisson ratios still assumed constants and set to $\nu_r = 0.49$ for rubber and $\nu_f = 0.3$ for fiber.

Table 1: Strain intervals of the constituents

Rubber				
Strain intervals	$0 \leq \epsilon \leq 9$ %	$9 < \epsilon \leq 140$ %	$140 < \epsilon \leq 265$ %	$\epsilon > 265$ %
Slope values $E_r^{(i)}$ $i = 1$ to 4	3.6 MPa	1.3 MPa	2.2 MPa	3.6 MPa

Aramid fiber			
Strain intervals	$0 \leq \epsilon \leq 6.5$ %	$6.5 < \epsilon \leq 11.5$ %	$\epsilon > 11.5$ %
Slope values $E_f^{(j)}$ $j = 1$ to 3	1574 MPa	3040 MPa	4220 MPa

Consequently, the homogenization technique shall be performed nine times to compute the equivalent homogenized anisotropic behavior corresponding to nine possible combinations of the constituents moduli. For this purpose we used the software "LANDRU" [6].

In tables 2.1 to 2.3 are presented the orthotropic elastic moduli corresponding to only three combinations. The fiber's volume ratio still unchanged and equals to 36 %.

Tables 2_1 to 3: Homogenized behavior

$E_r = 1.3 \text{ MPa}$		$E_f = 1574 \text{ MPa}$		$V_f = 36 \%$	
$E_2 \text{ (MPa)}$	$E_3 \text{ (MPa)}$	ν_{23}	ν_{12}	$G_{23} \text{ (MPa)}$	$G_{12} \text{ (MPa)}$
5.800	577.442	0.00409	0.912	0.945	0.787

$E_r = 2.2 \text{ MPa}$		$E_f = 3040 \text{ MPa}$		$V_f = 36 \%$	
$E_2 \text{ (MPa)}$	$E_3 \text{ (MPa)}$	ν_{23}	ν_{12}	$G_{23} \text{ (MPa)}$	$G_{12} \text{ (MPa)}$
9.621	1112.030	0.00363	0.914	1.596	1.332

$E_r = 3.6 \text{ MPa}$		$E_f = 4200 \text{ MPa}$		$V_f = 36 \%$	
$E_2 \text{ (MPa)}$	$E_3 \text{ (MPa)}$	ν_{23}	ν_{12}	$G_{23} \text{ (MPa)}$	$G_{12} \text{ (MPa)}$
15.730	1544.026	0.00427	0.913	2.611	2.180

In these tables, the 3-axis and 2-axis are the longitudinal (fiber direction) and transversal (perpendicular to the fiber direction) directions respectively. The 1-axis completes the direct orthonormal (1,2,3)-local orthotropic basis of the reinforced composite ply.

The anisotropic Poisson coefficients and the anisotropic shear moduli are denoted respectively by ν_{ij} and G_{ij} .

Nine finite element analyses were actually performed with the nine possible combinations listed above. These analyses show that the above three cases were sufficient to describe the whole response of the structure and insure satisfactory correlation between numerical and experimental results.

We shall notice that one more refined partition of strain domains of the constituents induces more and more combinations to consider. Hence, the refinement depends closely on the objectives and on the accuracy of the experimental measurements. The multilinear domain approach is summarized as indicated in fig. 3 in which we denoted by Q^c and Q^e the computed and experimental values, respectively, of any quantity Q .

In our case, three stages were necessary to reach the maximum load value, $P_{\max} = 0.39 \text{ MPa}$.

Finite Element Modeling

Let us denote by Ω the region occupied by the axisymmetric slice of the structure, related to a system of orthonormal axes (O, x_1, x_2, x_3) . Ω is subjected to an internal pressure P_i on a portion Γ_i of the boundary Γ . In this problem we neglect the body forces (such as gravity). On the others parts of the boundary, as could be seen from Fig. 1, we impose a zero displacement condition on Γ_0 , kinematics symmetry condition on Γ_s and a stress free condition on the complementary portion of the boundary Γ_e .

Fig. 3: Multilinear Domain Approach

Numerical method and tools employed

Following the classical process used for hyperelastic materials (P.G. Ciarlet [7]), the problem to be solved is transferred on the reference configuration Ω_0 considered as a natural one. On Ω_0 , the problem to be solved writes as follows :

$$\text{div}_0(F\Sigma) = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega_0 \quad (1)$$

$$\Sigma = QE \quad \text{in } \Omega_0 \quad (2)$$

$$F = 1 + \text{grad}_0(u) \quad 2E = {}^tFF - 1 \quad (3)$$

$$u_3 \text{ (or } u_z) = 0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma_s^0 \quad (4)$$

$$u = 0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma_0^0 \quad (5)$$

$$(F\Sigma) \cdot n_0 = -P_i n_0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma_i^0 \quad (6)$$

$$(F\Sigma) \cdot n_0 = 0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma_e^0 \quad (7)$$

Where Σ denotes the symmetric second Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor Q is the homogenized stiffness matrix, F the gradient deformation tensor, E The deformations tensor and n the external outer normal to the domain. The differential operators (divergence and gradient) indexed by 0 are applied on the natural configuration:

To solve the nonlinear problem (1)-(7), we used the Actualized Lagrangian. That approach is based essentially on sharing into a finite number K , the total loading. Let us denote by:

$$(\delta P)^n = (\alpha^{n+1} - \alpha^n)P_i$$

the pressure loading of each step and α^n being defined as follows :

$$0 = \alpha^0 < \alpha^1 < \dots < \alpha^n < \alpha^{n+1} < \dots < \alpha^K = 1$$

The method performed consists in the computation of the successive approximations u^n of the exact solution associated to the successive loading values. The $(n-1)$ th approximation is supposed known after the previous step. Thus, at each step we compute the displacement increase u^{*n} , solution around the known Ω_n -configuration.

Those problems are obtained at the step n by distinguishing in the deformation history of the structure three configurations : two of them are supposed known (Ω_0 , the initial one and Ω_n the just computed one), the third is the searched one Ω_{n+1} as it can be seen on fig. 4.

Fig. 4 : The different configurations considered

Using the kinematics process described, one can express the different tensors entering the problem to be solved at the $(n+1)$ th step as follows :

$$F^n = 1 + \text{grad}_0 u^n$$

$$F^{n+1} = 1 + \text{grad}_0 u^n + \text{grad}_0 u^{*n} = F^n + \text{grad}_0 u^{*n}$$

$$E^n = 1/2(t F^n F^n - 1)$$

$$E^{n+1} = E^n + E^{*n}$$

$$E^{*n} = 1/2(t F^n \text{grad}_0 u^{*n} + t \text{grad}_0 u^{*n} F^n + t \text{grad}_0 u^{*n} \text{grad}_0 u^{*n})$$

$$\Sigma^n = Q E^n$$

$$\Sigma^{n+1} = \Sigma^n + \Sigma^{*n}$$

$$\text{where, } \Sigma^{*n} = Q E^{*n}$$

Consequently, the problem obtained at the step $(n+1)$ can be written on the natural configuration by using the expressions above and lastly, knowing the n -th configuration the

problem is transferred on the Ω_n configuration. In order to realize this operation, let us denote Φ^n the tensor defined on Ω_0 as follows :

$$\Phi^n = \Phi^n \Sigma^{*n} + \text{grad}_0 u^{*n} (\Sigma^n + \Sigma^{*n}) \text{ and its image in } \Omega_n \Sigma^n = [\Phi^n \text{ }^t \Phi^n] / \det(\Phi^n)$$

Then, the use of the Piola's identity, applied to Φ^n , allows one to express the problem on the deformed configuration Ω_n . This way, the displacement increment u^{*n} has to satisfy the following equations :

$$\text{div}_n \Sigma^n = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega_n \quad (8)$$

$$\Sigma^{*n} = Q E^{*n} \quad \text{in } \Omega_n \quad (9)$$

$$2E^{*n} = \text{}^t F^n (\text{grad}_n u^{*n} F^n) + \text{}^t (\text{grad}_n u^{*n} F^n) F^n + \text{}^t (\text{grad}_n u^{*n} F^n) (\text{grad}_n u^{*n} F^n) \quad \text{in } \Omega_n \quad (10)$$

$$u_3^{*n} = 0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma_s^n \quad (11)$$

$$u^{*n} = 0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma_0^n \quad (12)$$

$$\Sigma^n \cdot n_n = -(\delta P)^n n_n - P_i \alpha^{n+1} (\text{tr}(\text{grad}_n u^{*n}) 1 - \text{grad}_n u^{*n}) \cdot n_n \quad \text{on } \Gamma_P^n \quad (13)$$

$$\Sigma^n \cdot n_n = 0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma_e^n \quad (14)$$

where the differential operators indexed by n act on the deformed configuration Ω_n . To solve this nonlinear problem we used the so-called Full Newton Algorithm. The displacement and energy parameters chosen for the convergence assessment have been respectively set to 10^{-3} and 10^{-2} .

For the mesh design three-dimensional first order (linear) isoparametric finite elements (8-nodes) for large strain analysis were used: 2 finite elements across the thickness of each reinforced ply and three elements across the rubber envelops thickness were created (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Mesh design of the structure

The mesh was refined until the asymptotic response of the numerical model was reached. Thus, 1294 finite elements were generated and the problem size is of 5500 degrees of freedom. The calculation was performed on a quadri-processors Convex C240 and the computer time consumed equals to 713 seconds.

Presentation and analysis of results

Considering the experimental uncertainties, the fundamental parameters defined for the validity test (see fig. 3) was set to $\alpha = \beta = 0.08$.

When the equivalent homogenized mechanical behavior of reinforced plies is determined by introducing the elastic moduli of the fiber and the rubber matrix only around the origin, i.e., only stage 1 (see fig. 3) is processed the numerical and measured results of the radial component of the displacement field at M (see fig. 1) and the z-component of the total reaction force on the pinned face Γ_0 (see Fig. 6) are in good agreement until the load value reaches 0.3 bars. Beyond that value the computed structure becomes more flexible than the physical one.

Fig. 6: Computed and experimental z-reaction force.

Fig. 7: Computed and experimental z-reaction force. MDA performed

Fig. 7 shows the same results when the Multilinear Domain Approach is performed. We notice the fairly good agreement until the maximum loading value between the computed and measured results. For illustration, fig. 8 shows the computed deformed structure and the Von-Mises stress distribution corresponding to the maximum value of the internal pressure imposed to the structure. An accurate analysis of that distribution shows that the critical value is localised around the free extremities of the reinforced plies. Experimental observations showed that damage and failure actually initiate in this area.

Figure 8. Von Mises Stress field on the displaced structure

Concluding remarks

Two approaches were proposed, the Incremental Homogenization Method and the Multilinear Domain Approach to include in the finite element model of any reinforced composite material and structure the nonlinearities of the reinforcements and the matrix.

This new *strategy* led us to a satisfactory computed results according to their comparison with the measured ones and was extended successfully to others loading types such as tensile, compression combined or not with internal pressure.

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